

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF HOUSING PROVISION IN THE ERADICATION OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROBLEMS AND ACHIEVEMENT OF MILLENNIUM DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN NIGERIA:
A CASE STUDY OF OSUN STATE

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ABSTRACT

The problem of inadequate housing which is associated with socio-economic problem of different kinds has been a recurrent decimal in the Nigerian housing situation. There have been several promises such as 'housing for all by 2000' and many unrealistic policy directives on housing provision. There is a general consensus on the fact that housing has central importance to everyone's quality of life and health with considerable economic, socio-cultural significance. Housing, being one of the three basic necessities of life, constitutes priority in the eradication of socio-economic problems. The intervention of public and private sectors in addressing housing need is imperative. The paper focuses on accessibility to standard housing as a vehicle of eradication of socio-economic problems. Also, it aims at finding out the relationship between housing and socio-economic problems in the natural economy. The paper further reveals seven components of major benefits of housing in eradication of socio-economic problems. Furthermore, it examines the role of effective urban development policy that will enhance adequate housing provision. The research also indicates housing as a pillar to improve both local and national economy and development of capacity of socio-economic base of the nation especially in the poorly developed economic situations. The paper concludes from the analysis of the operation of Osun State community-based poverty reduction agency, which indicates the significance of housing as vehicle to eradicate socio-economic problems through infrastructure provisions for various communities in different local governments of the state.

Keywords: Housing, Provision, Economy, Development, Poverty, Eradication

INTRODUCTION

A world where the poorest groups are able to live in a quality of life and health with considerable economic, social and cultural significance is a possibility. Housing fulfils several socio-economic objectives; it provides investment opportunities, offers shelter and privacy. Olugbenga and Olawoye (2007) give a more comprehensive definition and significance of housing. Housing has much more than physical structure; it has become a subject of highly socio-economic investment.

The significance of housing in Osun State and even in the entire country is noteworthy. Housing occupies the largest proportion of land use in towns and cities. However, many urban and rural dwellers still do not have access to quality housing due to poor economic base.

Rapid urbanization in Nigeria has created a rising need for shelter, which has led to a dramatic shift in the nature of poverty. Housing is the very issue that shapes the very pattern of national economic growth, the settlement of vast population, and the social and political stability of the nation.

The classic view of significance of housing as presented in economics includes economic growth as one of its essential aspect. Also, the complex inter-depended changes in the quality of life and of society as a whole which carry society forward according to prevailing adequate housing (Kuklinski, 1972). Economic growth has to do with increased growth in the overall economy and involves increased housing rather than human being. Housing also involves the process by which per capital output of a country is increased on a sustained basis, thereby raising the level of income.

The study of significance of housing is necessary if Nigeria is to achieve an overall socio-economic development as a precondition for achieving millennium development goal. Griffin (1981) observed that infrastructure plays two usual roles in the eradication of socio-economic problem.

Firstly, it contributes to the improvement of the quality of life and secondly, it facilitates production, thereby contribution to overall national economic development. Housing in this context should be viewed to be more than a source of satisfaction but as a means to national development, it should be viewed as an incentive to achieve higher standard of living and tool to eradicate socio-economic problems.

HOUSING IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

Firstly, emphasis is placed on housing because it is one of man's basic needs. A vigorous and buoyant housing sector is an indication of a strong programme of national investment and indeed the foundation to future economic growth and social development.

The gross housing delivering is therefore a major factor in the nation's gross domestic product (GDP) and indeed, this reflects the mirror and the barometer of the state of health of the nation. Economic activities are well known to encompass all aspects of human endeavour that are directed towards the creation of wealth. It is also known to enhance our self-worth by improving our living standards.

Economic growth is therefore a national pursuit in any human set-up as such improvement is expected to lead to increased wealth and prosperity both for individual and the whole nation. Despite international support and domestic investment in housing provision since the colonial era to date, Nigeria's housing problem still remains intractable. In fact, access to decent shelter has worsened for increasing segment of the urban population in Nigeria. It was reported that out of 121,000 housing units scheduled to be built between 1994-1995, only 1014 were completed (CBN, 1990 & 1998 & Vision 2000 main report). It was estimated that about 85% of urban residents live in single rooms, and the member of occupants per room range from 8 to 12 with adverse effects on their health.

Analysis of government's response to housing in Osun State Government at both federal and state levels have been insufficient for adequate and affordable housing for the population of Osun State despite the goals, policies and programmes put in place by them. The third tiers of governance in the country, the local governments, have not been actively involved in housing provision due to long term nature of recouping cost on investment in housing.

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HOUSING AND POVERTY

Poor people are frequently described as living in poverty but nothing has been done to directly improve their living conditions. Perhaps, this is because the important of secure, good quality housing to poor people has been underestimated. Benefits that housing programme can bring in terms of cost saving, income generation and economic development have also been overlooked. Indeed, most development professions assume that poverty is caused by lack of income, but fail to recognize that poor quality, overcrowded housing which lacks basic infrastructure are associated with poverty. For poor people, the struggle for shelter and housing comprises one of those fundamental elements of their daily survival strategy (*Ruth et al, 1998*).

Secure, safe housing with supporting infrastructure provides a wide range of benefits. These include increased health, security, social well-being of the people, especially women and are often prioritized above other forms of investment. Housing and infrastructural need can be classified under the following categories:

- (i) Physical infrastructure (Residential and other utilities)
- (ii) Social infrastructure (School, health centre, etc.)
- (iii) Economic infrastructure (Agro-industrial development, etc.)
- (iv) Institutional infrastructure (Banks, vocational training centre) (Arayela, 2002).

INFRASTRUCTURAL PROVISION AND ERADICATION OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROBLEM IN OSUN STATE

One of the most important trends in international development assistance is the increasing role of non-governmental organization. In shelter provision and the improvement of housing and economics of urban residents in Osun State, with growing commitment and financial contribution, the non-governmental

organizations are forging new relationships with aid agencies, forming an enhanced participatory role in the infrastructural provision (Richard May, 1995).

In Osun State, African Development Bank has fostered support specifically for infrastructural provision to improve living conditions of the poor and eradication of socio-economic problems. The supervisory agency, known as Osun State Community Based Poverty Reduction Agency has also utilized enhanced financial participant role in the developmental process in which 10 percent of financial commitment of a particular project be made available by the community and 90 percent will be contributed by the agency.

This strategic approach of infrastructural provision has enabled job creation and local economic empowerment, slum reduction and capacity building for cottage industries. In lieu of the weak economic base, high unemployment rate and poverty, infrastructural provision initiative has improved income of the urban residents to enhance their capacity. The following are the initiated projects by Osun State Community Based Poverty Reduction Project at different local governments that have been completed.

PROJECTS DISTRIBUTION ON ZONAL AND LOCAL GOVERNMENT BASIS FOR THE 1ST TO 7TH BATCHES OF PROJECTS

OSUN	ZONE	LGA	Edu.	Health	Agric.	Water	Elect.	Road/	Skill Acquisition	Market Dev.	Total
CENTRAL	IKIRUN	Boripe	2	2	-	1	1	-	-	-	6
		Ifelodun	2	-	-	2	-	1	-	-	5
		Odo-Otin	5	-	2	3	-	-	2	3	15
		Ila	-	-	-	1	2	-	1	-	4
		Ifedayo	1	-	-	1	2	-	1	-	5
		Boluwaduro	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	1	4
	OSOGBO	Osogbo	3	-	-	3	4	3	-	1	14
		Olorunda	2	1	-	3	1	1	1	-	9
		Irepodun	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	6
		Orolu	-	2	-	6	-	-	-	1	9
EAST	IFE	Ife East	-	3	-	2	2	1	-	-	8
		Ife Central	-	1	-	1	2	1	-	-	5
		Ife South	1	-	-	-	3	-	-	1	5
		Ife North	2	-	-	2	1	-	-	-	5
		Ife East (Area Off)	2	-	-	-	2	2	-	-	6
		ILESA	Ilesa West	2	-	-	-	2	2	-	2
	Ilesa East		2	-	1	-	2	-	1	-	6
	Obokun		-	-	1	6	1	1	1	-	11
	Oriade		3	-	-	2	-	1	-	-	6
	WEST	EDE	Atakumosa W	-	1	-	3	1	1	-	-
Atakumosa E			1	2	-	2	-	-	-	-	5
IWO	Ede South		2	-	-	2	2	1	-	-	7
	Ede North		2	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	5
	Ejigbo		1	1	-	2	1	-	-	-	5
	Egbedore		2	-	-	2	4	-	1	-	9
	Ayedaade	2	-	-	6	2	-	-	-	10	
Iwo	1	2	-	1	1	-	-	1	6		
Olaoluwa	3	-	-	2	1	-	-	2	8		
Ayedire	-	1	1	4	-	-	-	1	7		
Irewole	2	-	-	6	2	-	-	-	10		
Isokan	-	-	-	4	5	-	-	-	9		
GRAND TOTAL			48	18	6	72	44	15	8	13	224

SOURCE: OSUN STATE COMMUNITY BASED POVERTY ERADICATION AGENCY

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings reveal that housing provision in different local governments of the state has enhanced the standard of living of residents and their socio-economic development. At the 24 local governments where classrooms have been constructed and residential houses for teachers and youth corps members, learning process has been conducive. It was reported at Ayedaade that before the construction of residential housing for youth corps members, they usually deserted the schools because of poor living conditions.

Also, 12 local governments experienced construction of community health centres and residential housing for health workers. This supported the general notion that health is wealth. As people stay healthy, they can be active at work but a sick person will be less productive and thus, reduce the socio-economic development.

Agro-economic development was carried out in some of the local governments which also serve as employment generation for both skilled agric workers and unskilled labour. Market development which stemmed to 9 local governments has enhanced great contribution to socio-economic development, acts of buying could not be confined to open space, market development has made it possible to establish socio-economic interactions.

Furthermore, skill acquisition centres have been a major development centre in 7 local governments which has adequately developed people's socio-economic developments at different trades. It is noteworthy that housing provisions process is labour intensive, thereby providing employment for unskilled individuals that would have been a burden to national economy.

IMPORTANCE OF HOUSING IN ERADICATION OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROBLEM

There are several reasons why housing cannot be ignored in national development. Among other reasons, it is a fact that housing infrastructure accommodates both small and large scale industries. The smaller scale industries include tailoring, textile weaving, rice and corn millings, grinding of various kinds, cassava processing, artistic work, etc. The larger scale industries are agro-industrial development, poultry, fisheries, etc. (Arayela, 2002).

Housing in another context stimulates directly and indirectly, Social stability, employment, health, efficiency and ultimate development of an individual. Another importance of housing is the close relationship that exists between housing and economic productivity. In some local government surveyed in Osun State hostilities and tension which frustrate economic activities are traceable, in part, to housing problem.

The way in which housing is provided and exchanged has an impact over development goal such as equity and poverty eradication, construction techniques and location of housing can influence environmental stability and sustainability. The design of housing both reflects and protects important elements of culture and quality of life.

There is also a consensus on the role of housing construction in employment generation, particularly for unskilled labour, which is equally important in the economy of developing countries. Housing therefore should not only be seen as a service function but also as an instrument that contributes to economic development, the physical element of housing including facilities that give appropriate shape to the physical environment, thereby motivating people towards greater economic productivity.

The increasing stress of government to pursue right policies and improve the capacity of housing delivery as a result of demand from other aspects of national development is important for effective socio-economic development. Housing should not be looked at as a problem area requiring major social spending but as a vehicle to promote and economic activities particularly as a tool for eradication of socio-economic problem; income and employment opportunities generated by housing construction are amplified by multiplier effect in the economy (Erguden, 2001).

Therefore, an integrated development strategy must recognize the role and significance of housing since no development can be effected if the people are principal participants in the development and are forced to live in substandard houses, thus worsening the condition (Arayela, 2002).

BENEFITS OF HOUSING AND ERADICATION OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROBLEM

The role of housing in poverty eradication is potentially significant because of the range and number of benefits associated with it. Effective housing initiatives lead to improvement in health, safety, education, household

income and national economic productivity. In most cases, these housing initiatives have proved highly cost effective. Ruth *et al* (1998) in her report has identified the following benefits:

(a) **Improved health and safety**

Poor quality housing imposes enormous health and safety cost on its users. Significant loss of income and expenses on medical treatment as a result of negative impact of the housing on people, such as many infections and parasitic diseases, and disease vectors, are known to be associated with substandard housing. In addition, combination of overcrowding, the use of open fires or kerosene stove leads to danger from burns, scalding and accidental fires. These conditions are also associated with poor respiratory health; the upgraded housing scheme can greatly reduce health and safety risks faced by poor people. The income and expenses spent on medical treatment may be spent on other facilities and amenities that will improve the quality of life of people. Adequate housing will have positive impact on people which will reduce expenses on medical treatment.

(b) **Increased household income by creating a significant asset base**

The socio-economic problems of people are increased by the negative impact of substandard insecure housing. The day-to-day expenses that poor people face in meeting their shelter needs are considerably high, e.g., supply of electricity, water can also be extremely expensive. Often, the most expensive item of poor people expenditure is rent and for many tenant-households, this takes up more than third of their income. In some cases, it exceeds the amount required to repay a housing loan.

With secured, adequate housing, families extend their homes over time, the extensions accommodate small businesses or extra rooms are rented out. This becomes an asset base which increases household income. With secure tenure, it also becomes easier for legal water, electricity and sewer connection to be made, then legal home can be used as collateral to secure loans which can be invested in income generating activities, leading to further improvements of the quality of life.

(c) **Enhanced physical, mental and social development**

Substandard and unsecured housing especially where overcrowded living condition prevails and forced evictions for many poor families who were forced to move from one inadequate location to another. The lack of security has a particularly deleterious effect on health and development. On the other hand, safe, secure housing bring tremendous benefits for physical, mental and social development.

(d) **Provision of a focus for community development**

Poor communities who work together to address their housing problem often develops the capacity to successfully negotiate additional resources and service from government agencies which may respond to specific need. For example, improved housing for health workers, housing for teaching staff in a community, construction of domestic industry. This will lead to the development of effective community organization and development of economic base of the people.

NIGERIA URBAN DEVELOPMENT POLICY

Nigeria's urban centres are characterized by poorly developed economic base, high level of unemployment, poverty and slum habitation. Thus, urban housing development is identified as a key factor in the priority intervention area of government's policy. The policy envisages not only the provision of decent urban housing to citizens but also the utilization of the housing as an instrument to promote urban development, create jobs, improve the local urban economy, and develop the capacity of the domestic construction industry.

The policy objectives:

- Provide adequate housing both in terms of quality and quantity.
- Reduce slum dwelling.
- Reduce urban unemployment and poverty.
- Enhance and build the capacity of the domestic construction industry.
- Promote urban areas as engines of economic growth by increasing their contribution to GDP growth.
- Promote development of the private sector policy.

Strategy and role of government:

- Provision of land and infrastructure for housing buyers.
- Facilitating housing finance to cities and home buyers.

- Capacity building support to private construction firms.
- Development and provision of cost effective construction technologies that help ensure affordability by wider segment of urban dwellers.

CONCLUSION

In order to achieve a comprehensive and improved socio-economic empowerment that will aid the achievement of millennium development goals in Nigeria, the paper has highlighted housing as a major priority. Government must embrace effective and steady housing programme at the three levels of government. Furthermore, private investors and informal approach to housing provision must be harnessed.

The role of non-governmental organizations at various levels of infrastructural provision as experienced in Osun State Community Based Poverty Reduction Agency must be implemented.

Implementation of urban development policies listed above is essential for housing provisions that will provide effective socio-economic development.

Conceptualization of housing as physical structures for human satisfaction alone will inhibit socio-economic development therefore, housing must be conceived as “a vehicle to enhance socio-economic development in Nigeria”.

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